

Building A Creative Economy Educational Tourism of Kampung Coklat in Blitar Regency in Facing Non Military Threats

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ABSTRACT: A creative economy is a concept in developing the economy in the modern era by prioritizing ideas, ideas on creativity, and product innovation. The creative economy aspect is not limited to a few things, but everything that can be processed through creativity to create new value (creating value). The Central Bureau of National Statistics has mapped 16 creative economic sectors that continue to develop in Indonesia. The contribution of the creative economy sector in agriculture can be used as a unique educational tour through its superior products. Kampung Chocolate Educational Tourism in Blitar Regency is one of the creative economies that has a positive impact on community empowerment, education, economy, and social life. Through a qualitative descriptive study, This journal aims to explain how to build a creative economy based on educational tourism in Kampung Brown in the face of non-military threats, especially in the social and economic fields. The participation of this destination can provide employment, increase the income of the surrounding community, and increase the regional income of the Blitar Regency. As an agricultural area, there are many potential areas in Blitar that must be empowered optimally. Therefore, industrial strategy, destination strategy, marketing strategy, and institutional strategy are the responsibility of the government and the community as partners in conducting research, knowledge transfer, assistance, and policy recommendations.

KEYWORDS: Strategy, Creative Economy, Educational Tourism, Non-Military Threats

I. INTRODUCTION

A creative economy is a modern economic concept that emphasizes creativity and product innovation. This concept places human resources as the main actor in production by prioritizing ideas, ideas, and contemporary thoughts. Development is carried out with the development by each region of the creative economy as part of the realization of Law Number 24 concerning the Creative Economy.

The ASEAN Economic Community (MEA) has been running since 2015 providing dynamic challenges over time. The potential of Indonesia's economy must be cultivated with skills in being creative and innovating. Technology and information play an important role in optimizing the micro, small and medium enterprise (UMKM) sector. Indonesia's economic development through modernization is framed in the form of creative industries. This is in accordance with Alvin Toffler's theory that economic civilization is divided into three successive waves including agricultural economy, industrial economy, and information economy. As predicted, the fourth economic wave will come namely, the creative economy wave whose main orientation is creative ideas and ideas (Anggraini, 2008).

In international records, it is said that Indonesia, which is rich in natural resources, customs, and culture, is one of the world's tourism destinations. Tourism is a complex behavior as stated by Wardiyanta (2006) that tourism is an experience, tourism is a social behavior, tourism is a geographical phenomenon, tourism is a business, tourism is a resource, and tourism is an industry. Tourism is a source of increasing regional and national income.

The economic aspect caused by tourism is the contribution of foreign exchange from local and foreign tourist visits. While the social aspects that arise from tourism are employment, appreciation of arts, traditions, and national culture (Muljadi AJ, 2009). Developing the creative economy of the tourism sector requires optimal planning and is supported by various parties such as the community and government. Planning for tourism development requires industrialization, destination, marketing, and institutional strategies.

Blitar Regency is an area that has high potential in a tourism-based creative economy. Kampung Chocolate is one of the potential creative economy businesses that are able to provide the most popular tourism education. Educational tourism can be attractive by highlighting education. The educational process carried out in tourism activities uses active and creative learning methods, as well as alternative effective learning methods (Tim Pengabdian Masyarakat, 2017).

The development of the creative economy aims to build the economy and also as an anticipation of the currents of globalization that bring about Strategic environmental issues that are increasingly difficult to predict. Indonesia as a country that benefits from various aspects which include food wealth, biological/non-biological natural resources must be able to face all forms of threats, especially non-military threats in the economic field.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Economic Development

Development is the process of raising or improving all systems social, economic, political, culture, infrastructure, science and technology, education, defense, and others with the aim of making human life feasible (Abe, 1994). According to (Irawan and Suparmoko, 2002), economic development is a series of efforts to improve the standard of living of a nation, the high and low of which is measured by real per capita income. Economic development according to (Arsyad, 2004) defined the main elements and characteristics in economic development which include:

- a. The process is considered as a continuous change.
- b. Efforts to increase per capita income.
- c. Long-term sustainability of the increase in per capita income.
- d. Improvement of the institutional system in the economic, political, legal, social, and cultural fields through institutional and regulatory aspects (legal formal and informal).

2.2. Creative Economy

The creative economy is a sector that focuses on creating economic value through the creative process of an individual. (First Dictum of Presidential Instruction No. 6 of 2009 concerning Creative Economy Development). The creative economy is essentially an economic activity that puts forward creative thinking to create something new and different that has value and commercial (Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy: Medium-Term Action Plan 2015-2019). Law No. 24 of 2019 concerning the Creative Economy explains that the purpose of the creative economy is to optimize the creativity of human resources based on cultural heritage, science, and/or technology.

2.3. Educational Tour

Educational tourism is a tourism activity carried out by tourists with the aim of obtaining education and learning. Educational tourism activities are quite varied, including getting to know schools, customs, learning languages, seminars, and research activities, as well as business activities. The characteristics of educational tourism are as follows:

- a. The place has a distinctive tourist attraction.
- b. Educational programs can be for students and universities.
- c. There is a tour guide (Tim Pengabdian Masyarakat, 2017).

2.4. Non-Military Threat

Non-military threats in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2002 concerning Defense are called non-military threats, which are a form of threat that uses non-military factors which are considered to endanger sovereignty, territorial integrity, and safety of the entire nation and state. Non-military threats can come from abroad or can come from within the country. The forms of non-military threats in Indonesia that have the potential to disrupt national stability and integration according to the Indonesian Defense White Paper (2015) include threats in the fields of ideology, politics, economy, socio-culture, technology, public safety, and threats with legislative dimensions. Aspects that must be regulated in dealing with non-military threats are laws and regulations, management, and community empowerment (wantimpres.go.id, 2017).

2.5. Strategy

Strategy is a pattern or planning that combines objectives, policies, and a series of activities in a unified whole to achieve the organizational goals that have been set (Avianti, 2015). The strategy in developing tourism cannot be separated from the existence of tourist attractions until there is a type of development that is supported by the provision of facilities and accessibility. The Blitar Regency Government (2017) strategy in developing tourism potential consists of:

- a. The industrial strategy consists of strengthening the structure of the tourism industry, increasing the competitiveness of tourism products, developing tourism business partnerships, creating business credibility, and developing environmental responsibility.
- b. Destination strategy consists of a regional system, functional area, and destination development.
- c. The marketing strategy consists of research on target markets and market competition, tourism product planning, price policy development, tourism product distribution, and promotion.
- d. The institutional strategy consists of strengthening institutional organizations, developing tourism human resources, developing multi-stakeholder participation.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this study, researchers used descriptive qualitative methods. Qualitative research methods are concerned with non-numerical data, collecting and analyzing narrative data. Qualitative research methods are mainly used to obtain rich data, in-depth information about the issue or problem to be solved. This study explores data through focus groups, in-depth interviews with the management team of Kampung Brown Blitar Regency, and observations that play a role in collecting data (Sugiono, 2018).

Qualitative research develops designs that are continuously adapted to the realities on the ground. So, do not use a design that has been compiled strictly and rigidly, so that it cannot be changed anymore. This is caused by several things. First, it is impossible to imagine in advance about the plural realities in the field. Second, it is impossible to predict in advance what will change because it will occur in the interaction between the researcher and reality. Third, the various related value systems relate in unpredictable ways. Thus, the

design, especially the problems that have been determined in advance if researchers go to the field, can be changed (Moleong LJ, 2019).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Good planning becomes a strategic policy in developing the tourism system. Through planning a company can define goals, set strategies to achieve goals, and develop work activity plans in achieving goals. Kampung Chocolate is one of the tourism destinations that packs an educational tourism model. The success of maintaining its existence to date is proof of the implementation of the right company development strategy.

Blitar Chocolate Village Educational Tourism is a creative economy potential that must receive attention through Law Number 24 of 2019 concerning the Creative Economy. Economic activities are carried out by empowering the surrounding community who have SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) in managing chocolate and handicrafts. Community empowerment efforts are ways to deal with non-military threats in the economic and social fields. Economically, the existence of Kampung Brown has provided employment opportunities for employees or the surrounding community, reduced unemployment, and increased community income and regional treasury. Meanwhile, socially the existence of Kampung Brown can improve the social welfare of the community and a conducive environment.

The positive impact is generated by reducing the number of unemployed. Unemployment becomes a psychological and psychological burden such as emotional pressure and unstable thoughts for the unemployed and their families (Ikawati, 2019). Ikawati added that the unemployed will have a bad feeling about their family and environment, there will be feelings of shame, guilt, moral burden, feeling useless, lack of self-confidence, irritability, and pressure due to the demands of their parents and family. The unemployed will do various ways to get a job and make ends meet. However, not a few of the unemployed end up committing acts that violate norms and laws in order to fulfill their needs, such as crimes or crimes.

The industrialization has become a strategy carried out by Kampung Chocolate Blitar Educational Tourism with the involvement of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in the surrounding community. Because it is based on a creative economy, people can be creative in processing various chocolate foods and making handicrafts. In this case, they are able to create added value to a product. Creative products are displayed and sold in the Blitar Chocolate Village Educational Tourism gallery as souvenirs for tourists. In addition, there are also outlets for various chocolate foods and beverages.

Along with modernization and global competition, Kampung Brown Blitar Educational Tour provides modern facilities including the availability of bathrooms, places of worship, as well as easy accessibility to the Kampung Brown Blitar Educational Tour because it has been given directions. All parties involved with tourism activities, both employees and the surrounding community, have a responsibility to preserve the environment and use environmentally friendly machines. So that managing the product does not interfere with the surrounding community.

Destinations are also a strategy for Kampung Chocolate Blitar Educational Tourism by offering tourism products in the form of educational tours. Educational tour packages accompanied by experienced tour guides. The destinations offered are small fish therapy in ponds that are beneficial for health, providing games for children, swimming pools, cooking classes, and entertainment stages. Kampung Chocolate Blitar Educational Tour also provides sharia lodging accommodation for tourists who want to rent a room or hold events.

In addition to industrialization and destinations, marketing is also the most important strategy in introducing it to the public. The first marketing strategy that was carried out was by setting the target market for Kampung Chocolate Blitar Educational Tourism ranging from children, teenagers, to the elderly. Promotions are carried out through various media, be it television, radio, or the internet, such as the official website as tourist information material before visiting, as well as social media such as Facebook and Instagram. In this way,

Kampung Chocolate Educational Tourism is quickly recognized by the wider community, both local and foreign tourists. In buying and selling product transactions, e-commerce services also provide ease of product transactions without having to come directly to the Kampung Chocolate Blitar Educational Tour.

Towards good corporate, institutional strategy. The institutional strategy is carried out by strengthening institutional organizations, namely establishing relationships and cooperation with the department to develop tourism management. The organizational structure is structured according to the skills possessed by employees and builds employees by providing education and training so that they can carry out their duties properly, and have good behavior in providing services to tourists.

Educational tourism is an activity carried out by tourists with the aim of obtaining education and learning. Educational tourism in the village of chocolate emphasizes learning for kindergarten, elementary, junior high, and high school children. He was taught from planting cocoa beans, processing chocolate, and packaging chocolate. The attraction of this place is the cacao and chocolate trees. Educational tours have various activities, ranging from getting to know schools, customs, learning languages, to seminars and research activities, as well as business activities.

Educational tourism has a positive impact on education. The concept of educational tourism becomes an active-creative learning method with hands-on practice. This can save the nation's generation from non-military threats in terms of culture. It is known that the rapid development of technology has an impact on digital colonization and the nation's culture. Indonesia is said to be in a reading emergency, which will worry the nation's future. With the literacy movement, schools are expected to be able to facilitate optimally through adapting mandatory activity programs: (1) implementing a 15-minute program of reading books other than textbooks before learning begins, (2) carrying out physical exercise activities such as SKJ which are carried out regularly and routinely at least once a week by all school members such as teachers, education staff, and students (Safitri et.al, 2020). Therefore, the existence of Educational Tourism in Blitar has helped in literacy movement according to the Regulation of the Minister of Educational and Culture Number 23 of 2015, but the difference is this isn't implemented in schools.

Along with the progress, the material taught by the Kampung Chocolate Blitar Educational Tour increased in the analysis of the cocoa plantation business. A creative economy is an economic activity that makes creativity, culture, cultural heritage, and the environment the foundation of the future. The important thing that the creative economy offers is the utilization of unlimited reserves of renewable resources, namely ideas, talents, and creativity (Moelyono, 2010). Through creativity, cocoa pods are produced to increase the selling value. Cocoa skin can also be used as handicraft.

The creative economy development process is related and interdependent with the main aspects, namely creative Human Resources (HR) with innovative thinking, innovation and creativity characterized by competitive local advantages, incentives for the development of creative economic products, technology using environmentally friendly methods, availability of materials local areas and optimizing their use, as well as accessibility and connectivity (networks) (Firdausy, 2017). This process is evidenced in the creations of the surrounding community who have SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) in collaboration with Kampung Chocolate Blitar Educational Tourism using a profit-sharing system by holding weekly evaluations, additional income for SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) in the form of cash raffles, sweepstakes Umrah, social gathering.

Optimization of utilization is needed in creating distinctive products such as food wrapped in chocolate, chocolate drinks, cocoa leather crafts, and others. The accessibility of the brown village with SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) from the surrounding community is very close so that it is easy to send creative economy products and connectivity or network with all SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) to hold associations.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion of the research above, several conclusions can be drawn regarding how to build a creative economy for educational tourism in the chocolate village in the face of non-military threats, including:

- a. In building a creative economy, the educational tour of the brown village requires the responsibility and participation of the surrounding community and the government in conducting research, knowledge transfer, assistance, and policy recommendations for modern development.
- b. The Educational Tourism of Kampung Cocoa, Blitar Regency, is a creative economy and tourism sector that optimizes community empowerment and micro, small and medium enterprises (UMKM) in processing cacao plants to be used as areas for entrepreneurship education and training. Services that can be provided include training and mentoring in cocoa processing, games, and education, as well as a business center.
- c. A creative economy based on educational tourism is able to face non-military threats through community empowerment. With this, it can create community welfare, employment to reduce unemployment; and increase literacy through education.

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